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Separation Workflow

Overall study design

Title of the study			
Elucidating molecular lipid perturbations in trigeminal neuralgia using cerebrospinal fluid lipidomics			
Document creation date	12/19/2024	Corresponding Email	dongyuan_xu@whu.edu.cn
Principal investigator	Nanxiang Xiong	Is the workflow targeted or untargeted?	Untargeted
Institution	Zhongnan Hospital of Wuhan University, Wuhan 430071, P. R. China	Clinical	Yes

Lipid extraction

Extraction method	2-phase system	Were internal standards added prior extraction?	Yes
pH adjustment	5% acetic acid water	Special conditions	-
2-phase system	Folch	Derivatization	-

Analytical platform

Ionization additives	Ammonium acetate	Resolution at m/z 200 at MS1	40000
Number of separation dimensions	One dimension	Mass accuracy in ppm at MS1	5
Separation type 1	LC	Recording mode of raw data at MS1	Centroid mode
Separation mode 1 (liquid)	RP	Mass window for precursor ion isolation (in Da total isolation window)	1
Detector	Mass spectrometer	Mass resolution for detected ion at MS2	High resolution
MS type	QTOF	Resolution at m/z 200 at MS2	20000
MS vendor	SCIEX	Mass accuracy in ppm at MS2	5
Ion source	ESI	Recording mode of raw data at MS2	Centroid mode
MS Level	MS1, MS2	Was/Were additional dimension/techniques used	No
Mass resolution for detected ion at MS1	High resolution		

Quality control

Blanks	Yes	Quality control	Yes
Type of Blanks	Extraction blank	Type of QC sample	Sample pool

Method qualification and validation

Method validation	No
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Reporting

Are reported raw data uploaded into repository?	Yes	Summary data	Quantification data
Link to repository / ID to entry	MetaboLights repository (MTBLS11086)	Raw data upload	No
Are metadata available?	No	Additional comments	-

Sample Descriptions

Trigeminal Neuralgia / Human / Other liquid material

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage time (month)	3
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Freeze-thaw cycles	0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No
Storage temperature	-80 °C		

Control / Human / Other liquid material

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage time (month)	3
Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Freeze-thaw cycles	0
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	30	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No
Storage temperature	-80 °C		

Lipid Class Descriptions

1) Cer[M-H]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	Cer	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Check on:	-
Identification level	Molecular species level	Limit of detection	No
Polarity mode	Negative	RT verified by standard	Yes
Type of negative (precursor)ion	[M-H]-	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	Yes
Fragments for identification		Model for separation prediction	Yes
Fragment name			
[LCB-H]			
[FA-H]			
[Cer-H2O]			
Isotope correction at MS1	No	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Lipid Identification Software	MS-DIAL
MS1 verified by standard	No	Data manipulation	-
MS2 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Background check at MS1	No	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Background check at MS2	No	Further identification remarks	-

1) Cer[M-H]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	MultiQuant
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass		
Cer d18:1-d7/15:0	Cer		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	One factor for all species	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	No		

2) FA[M-H]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	FA	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Check on:	-
Identification level	Molecular species level	Limit of detection	No
Polarity mode	Negative	RT verified by standard	Yes
Type of negative (precursor)ion	[M-H]-	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	Yes
Fragments for identification		Model for separation prediction	Yes
Fragment name			
[FA-H]			
[FA(-CO)]			
FA 18:1(+O)			
Isotope correction at MS1	No	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Lipid Identification Software	MS-DIAL
MS1 verified by standard	No	Data manipulation	-
MS2 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Background check at MS1	No	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Background check at MS2	No	Further identification remarks	-

2) FA[M-H]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	MultiQuant
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass		
FA 16:0(d4)	FA		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	One factor for all species	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	No		

3) LPC[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	LPC	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Check on:	-
Identification level	Molecular species level	Limit of detection	No
Polarity mode	Positive	RT verified by standard	Yes
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	Yes
Fragments for identification		Model for separation prediction	Yes
Fragment name			
[LPC(184)]			
-FA 16:0(-H)			
-LPC(74)			
Isotope correction at MS1	No	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Lipid Identification Software	MS-DIAL
MS1 verified by standard	No	Data manipulation	-
MS2 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Background check at MS1	No	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Background check at MS2	No	Further identification remarks	-

3) LPC[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	MultiQuant
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass		
LPC 18:1(d7)	LPC		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	One factor for all species	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	No		

4) SM[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	SM	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Check on:	-
Identification level	Molecular species level	Limit of detection	No
Polarity mode	Positive	RT verified by standard	Yes
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	Yes
Fragments for identification		Model for separation prediction	Yes
Fragment name			
[SM(184)]			
[LCB-H]			
-FA-H			
Isotope correction at MS1	No	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Lipid Identification Software	MS-DIAL
MS1 verified by standard	No	Data manipulation	-
MS2 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Background check at MS1	No	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Background check at MS2	No	Further identification remarks	-

4) SM[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	MultiQuant
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass		
SM 18:1;20/18:1(d9)	SM		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	One factor for all species	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	No		

5) PC[M+CH3COO]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PC	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Check on:	-
Identification level	Molecular species level	Limit of detection	No
Polarity mode	Positive	RT verified by standard	Yes
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+CH3COO]-	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	Yes
Fragments for identification		Model for separation prediction	Yes
Fragment name			
[PC(184)]			
-FA 18:1(-H)			
-PC(74)			
Isotope correction at MS1	No	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Lipid Identification Software	MS-DIAL
MS1 verified by standard	No	Data manipulation	-
MS2 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Background check at MS1	No	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Background check at MS2	No	Further identification remarks	-

5) PC[M+CH3COO]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	MultiQuant
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass		
PC 15:0_18:1(d7)	PC		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	One factor for all species	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	No		

6) PE[M-H]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PE	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Check on:	-
Identification level	Molecular species level	Limit of detection	No
Polarity mode	Negative	RT verified by standard	Yes
Type of negative (precursor)ion	[M-H]-	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	Yes
Fragments for identification		Model for separation prediction	Yes
Fragment name			
[PE(141)]			
-FA 20:4(-H)			
-PE(87)			
Isotope correction at MS1	No	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Lipid Identification Software	MS-DIAL
MS1 verified by standard	No	Data manipulation	-
MS2 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Background check at MS1	No	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Background check at MS2	No	Further identification remarks	-

6) PE[M-H]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	MultiQuant
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass		
PE 15:0_18:1(d7)	PE		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	One factor for all species	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	No		

7) MG[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	MG	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Check on:	-
Identification level	Molecular species level	Limit of detection	No
Polarity mode	Positive	RT verified by standard	Yes
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	Yes
Fragments for identification		Model for separation prediction	Yes
Fragment name			
[FA-H]			
[MG-H ₂ O]			
Isotope correction at MS1	No	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Lipid Identification Software	MS-DIAL
MS1 verified by standard	No	Data manipulation	-
MS2 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Background check at MS1	No	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Background check at MS2	No	Further identification remarks	-

7) MG[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	MultiQuant
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass		
MG 18:1(d7)	MG		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	One factor for all species	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	No		

8) DG[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	DG	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Check on:	-
Identification level	Molecular species level	Limit of detection	No
Polarity mode	Positive	RT verified by standard	Yes
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+NH4] ⁺	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	Yes
Fragments for identification		Model for separation prediction	Yes
Fragment name			
[FA-H]			
-FA 18:0(+HO)			
[DG-H2O]			
Isotope correction at MS1	No	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Lipid Identification Software	MS-DIAL
MS1 verified by standard	No	Data manipulation	-
MS2 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Background check at MS1	No	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Background check at MS2	No	Further identification remarks	-

8) DG[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	MultiQuant
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass		
DG 15:0_18:1(d7)	DG		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	One factor for all species	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	No		

9) TG[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	TG	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Check on:	-
Identification level	Molecular species level	Limit of detection	No
Polarity mode	Positive	RT verified by standard	Yes
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+NH4] ⁺	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	Yes
Fragments for identification		Model for separation prediction	Yes
Fragment name			
-FA 18:2(+HO) -TAG(17)			
TAG(17)			
FA 18:0(+HO)			
Isotope correction at MS1	No	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Lipid Identification Software	MS-DIAL
MS1 verified by standard	No	Data manipulation	-
MS2 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Background check at MS1	No	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Background check at MS2	No	Further identification remarks	-

9) TG[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	MultiQuant
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass		
TG 15:0_18:1_15:0(d7)	TG		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	One factor for all species	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	No		